

Electrophoretic Separation of -Ous and -Ic States of Metal Ions

Part I : Iron

H. G. MUKHERJEE and S. P. NAG

University College of Science, Calcutta

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Paper electrophoretic technique was employed for the separation of -ous and -ic states of iron. Instead of taking simple ferrous and ferric ions, cationic complexes like ferrous orthophenanthroline and ferrous dipyriddy as well as anionic complexes like hexacyanoferrate(II), hexacyanoferrate(III) and ferric-EDTA were taken for electrophoresis. Binary mixtures of these Fe(II) and Fe(III) complexes were separated successfully using 0.01N H₂SO₄, 0.05M disodium salt of EDTA, 0.1M lactic acid, 0.1M NH₄Cl and 0.025M tartaric acid as carrier electrolytes.

IT has been observed that simple -ous and -ic states of metal ions cannot be separated electrophoretically using paper as supporting medium with the exception of only a few. But separation of -ous and -ic states of metal ions was achieved by complexation of the ions before electrophoresis. This method was employed for the separation of ferrous and ferric ions by Lederer¹ who took ferro and ferricyanide complexes in 0.5N HCl carrier electrolyte. Lederer and Ward² examined the migration of ferro and ferri cyanide using 1M KCl as carrier electrolyte. Bigli and Trabaneli³ separated the $\alpha\alpha'$ dipyriddy complex of Fe(II) and Fe(III) ions using 1% Citric acid, 0.5% Sodium Potassium tartarate as carrier electrolyte. Fe(II)-Fe(III) separation has also been done by Bigli, Trabaneli and Panacaldi⁴; Fe(II) being complexed by $\alpha\alpha'$ -dypyriddy, Fe(III) as acetylacetonate complex using 1% Na-K-tartarate as carrier electrolyte.

In the previous communications^{5,6} electrophoretic separations of binary and ternary mixtures of ions have been reported. Present studies have been carried out with a view to separate the -ous and -ic states of ions.

To achieve this stable complexes of the ions are prepared prior to electrophoresis. Then a number of carrier electrolytes are taken and the stabilities of these complexes are judged from their electrophoretic migrations. Only those carrier electrolytes are taken for the separation of mixed -ous and -ic complexes in which both the species remained undecomposed. Moreover, choice of ligands for the complexation of -ous and -ic states was made in such a way as to form anionic complex with one ion while the other ion form cationic complex. Thus the difference in the direction of migration caused their separation successful by paper electrophoresis.

Separation of some anionic complexes of -ous and -ic states of these ions are also possible due to the difference in their mobilities. In the present paper

such separations of the different complexes of Fe(II) and Fe(III) have been reported.

Experimental

Apparatus used was of Wieland and Fischer⁷ type horizontal electrophoretic instrument. Paper strips (1 cm \times 34 cm) from Whatman No. 1, have been used as supporting medium.

Mohr's salt was first treated with hydroquinone to convert any trace amount of ferric ion to ferrous state and then treated with a saturated aqueous solution of orthophenanthroline (Orphen) which produced a red coloured ferrous-Orthophenanthroline complex. Anionic ferric E.D.T.A. complex was prepared by taking freshly precipitated Fe(OH)₃, washed properly to make it free from any anion and treated with 0.05M disodium salt of E.D.T.A. (A.R.) and then heated. To ascertain stability and sign of the charge of the complexes both the ferrous and ferric complexes were individually allowed to migrate in different carrier electrolytes. Electrophoretic migration revealed that they were stable only in the following electrolytes: 0.1N NH₄Cl, 0.01N H₂SO₄, 0.1M lactic acid, 0.025M tartaric acid and 0.05M disodium salt of E.D.T.A. Ferrous dipyriddy and ferrous orthophenanthroline from cationic complexes which moved as cation whereas ferric E.D.T.A. and ferricyanide formed anionic complexes and moved towards the anode. An attempt was made to separate the mixed -ous and -ic complexes. Equal volumes of ferric E.D.T.A. complex and ferrous Orthophenanthroline complex each of 10⁻²M concentration were mixed together and a drop of the soln. was electrophorised for about 2 hr in the above carrier electrolytes. Electropherogram showed two well separated zones—one at the cathode and the other at the anode.

Ferrous orthophenanthroline was mixed with potassium ferricyanide solution and a drop of the mixture was electrophorised for about one and a half

TABLE I—SEPARATION OF -OUS AND -IC STATES OF IRON IONS
 POTENTIAL GRADIENT 5.88 VOLTS/CM; DIMENSION OF PAPER STRIP (WHATMAN No. 1) = 34 cm × 1 cm.

Composition of Binary mixture	Separation sequences & position (rear & front) of the migrating zone from the point of application in Cm.	Carrier electrolyte	Time of run
[Fe(Orphen) ₃] ⁺² & [Fe(EDTA)] ⁻¹	[Fe(Orphen) ₃] ⁺² : [Fe(EDTA)] ⁻¹ -1.3 to -2.9 : +0.7 to +2.3	0.05M Na ₂ EDTA	2 hrs.
„	[Fe(Orphen) ₃] ⁺² : [Fe(EDTA)] ⁻¹ -2.7 to -4.4 : +0.5 to +2.2	0.1M Lactic Acid	3 hrs.
„	[Fe(Orphen) ₃] ⁺² : [Fe(EDTA)] ⁻¹ -1.3 to -4.0 : +0.5 to +3.0	0.01N H ₂ SO ₄	2.5 hrs.
„	[Fe(Orphen) ₃] ⁺² : [Fe(EDTA)] ⁻¹ -2.0 to -3.1 : +0.8 to +2.3	0.1N NH ₄ Cl	2 hrs.
„	[Fe(Orphen) ₃] ⁺² : [Fe(EDTA)] ⁻¹ -4.1 to -6.5 : +2.0 to +4.0	0.025M Tartaric acid	4 hrs.
[Fe(Orphen) ₃] ⁺² & [Fe(CN) ₆] ⁻³	[Fe(Orphen) ₃] ⁺² : [Fe(CN) ₆] ⁻³ -1.4 to -2.6 : +3.5 to +5.5	0.05M Na ₂ EDTA	1.5 hrs.
„	[Fe(Orphen) ₃] ⁺² : [Fe(CN) ₆] ⁻³ -1.0 to -3.5 : +1.0 to +5.0	0.01N H ₂ SO ₄	2 hrs.
„	[Fe(Orphen) ₃] ⁺² : [Fe(CN) ₆] ⁻³ -1.1 to -2.2 : +4.6 to +6.1	0.1N NH ₄ Cl	1.5 hrs.
[Fe(dipy) ₃] ⁺² & [Fe(CN) ₆] ⁻³	[Fe(dipy) ₃] ⁺² : [Fe(CN) ₆] ⁻³ -1.2 to -2.4 : +3.8 to +8.4	0.05M Na ₂ EDTA	2 hrs.
[Fe(dipy) ₃] ⁺² & [Fe(EDTA)] ⁻¹	[Fe(dipy) ₃] ⁺² : [Fe(EDTA)] ⁻¹ -5.1 to -8.0 : +0.9 to +2.8	0.1M Lactic acid	3 hrs.
[Fe(dipy) ₃] ⁺² & [Fe(EDTA)] ⁻¹	[Fe(dipy) ₃] ⁺² : [Fe(EDTA)] ⁻¹ -1.9 to -3.0 : +0.8 to +2.1	0.05M Na ₂ EDTA	2 hrs.
„	[Fe(dipy) ₃] ⁺² : [Fe(EDTA)] ⁻¹ -1.5 to -2.8 : +0.6 to +2.4	0.1N NH ₄ Cl	2 hrs.
[Fe(CN) ₆] ⁻⁴ & [Fe(EDTA)] ⁻¹	[Fe(EDTA)] ⁻¹ , [Fe(CN) ₆] ⁻⁴ +0.5 to +1.5 : +3.4 to +5.0	0.05M Na ₂ EDTA	2 hrs.

hour. Two well separated zones—one towards the cathode due to ferrous complex and the other towards the anode due to the ferricyanide ion were obtained. Less time is required for the separation of this pair as ferricyanide ion migrated very fast. Carrier-electrolytes used were 0.1N NH₄Cl, 0.05M disodium salt of E.D.T.A. and 0.01N H₂SO₄.

Ferrous dipyriddy [Fe(dipy)₃]⁺² cationic complex was prepared by treating Mohr's salt solution (free of ferric ion) with αα'-dipyridyl. This complex was found to be stable and cationic in 0.1N NH₄Cl, 0.05M disodium salt of E.D.T.A., 0.1M lactic acid and 0.01N H₂SO₄. Binary mixtures of ferric E.D.T.A. chelate and [Fe(dipy)₃]⁺² were subjected to electrophoresis in the above carrier electrolytes. Two well separated zones in each case were obtained.

Separation of -ous and -ic states of iron was also done by taking their anionic complexes. The complex carrying greater number of charges moved faster than the other, thus making the separation feasible. Potassium ferrocyanide solution was mixed with ferric E.D.T.A. anionic complex and were separated from each other after 1.5 hr electrophoresis in 0.05M disodium salt of E.D.T.A.

The reagents employed for the detection of Fe(II) and Fe(III) complexes were aqueous solns. of potassium ferricyanide and potassium ferrocyanide respectively. Ferrocyanide ion was detected with ferric chloride solution and ferricyanide with ferrous sulphate soln.

The results are summarised in the Table where '+' sign indicates the migration towards the anode, '-' sign towards the cathode and ':' sign point of application of the migrant.

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